

Research article

Stress and word order in Asian languages with reference to the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia*

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Abstract: This paper gives an overview of the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia* (LAA) (Endo et al. 2021) and examines the hypothesis of stress-order correlation (Tokizaki 2011 et seq.) based on its descriptions of Asian languages. Generalizing the idea of holistic typology by Bally (1944) (German vs. French) and Donegan and Stampe (1983) (Munda vs. Mon-Khmer), Tokizaki (2011 et seq.) proposes the hypothesis that word-stress location correlates with word order (head-initial/head-final) in the world's languages: languages with word-initial stress have head-final order (OV, postposition, suffixing, modifier-noun) while languages with word-final order have head-initial order (e.g. VO, preposition, prefixing, noun-modifier). In this paper, I examine the word-stress location in each group of Asian languages described in Chapter 7 on tone and accent in LAA. Analyzing more descriptions of stress in literature other than LAA and the word order data in Dryer (2013a, b, c, d, e, f, g) in the *World Atlas of Linguistic Structure Online* (WALS), I argue that the stress-order correlation hypothesis generally holds in Asian languages. It is also argued that word-stress location correlates with word order because the word-stress pattern is projected onto the phrase-stress pattern where the main stress universally falls on the complement rather than the head (e.g. on O rather than on V in a verb phrase) (cf. Cinque 1993).*

Keywords: *Linguistic Atlas of Asia*; word stress; word order; WALS; syntax-phonology interface

1. Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to show that word-stress location (initial/final) correlates with word order (head-final/head-initial) in Asian languages as well as other languages of the world, with reference to the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia* (LAA) (Endo et al. 2021) and the *World Atlas of Linguistic Structure Online* (WALS) (Haspelmath and Dryer 2013).

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In section 2, I briefly review two linguistic atlases WALS and LAA. Section 3 illustrates Chapter 7 on tone and accent in LAA and discusses the stress-order correlation hypothesis. Section 4 investigates the stress system of each Asian language group and examine the correlation between word-stress location and word order. In section 5, I briefly explain why word-stress location correlates with word order based on the minimalist program of linguistic theory (Chomsky 1995, 2012). Section 6 concludes the discussion.

2. Linguistic Atlases: WALS and LAA

2.1. *World Atlas of Linguistic Structure*

Publication of the *World Atlas of Linguistic Structure* (WALS) (Haspelmath et al. 2005) made much impact on the study of linguistic typology. The maps in WALS provide an excellent overview of the features of the world's languages. The accompanying CD-ROM, which contains data and interactive software, was also useful. In addition to this book, the online version of WALS was published in 2008 (Dryer and Haspelmath 2008), which greatly enhanced the usability of the maps and the data. Revised versions of WALS with minor corrections have been published periodically in 2011, 2013, 2014 and 2020.

2.2. *Linguistic Atlas of Asia*

A recently published atlas, the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia* (Endo et al. 2021, henceforth LAA) focuses on the languages in Asia. LAA is a box set consisting of a book and four sheets of A1-size maps (double-sided and folded to A5 size), which provide detailed descriptions of linguistic features. The book contains eight chapters, the first five of which discuss the lexical items 'sun,' 'rice plant,' 'milk,' 'wind,' and 'iron.' The other three chapters discuss word order (Ch. 6), prosodic features (Ch. 7) and sentence structure (Ch. 8). Each chapter starts with an overview of the item in Asia written by the author shown in (1).

- (1) Introduction (ENDO Mitsuaki)
 - Chapter 1: sun (FUKUSHIMA Chitsuko)
 - Chapter 2: rice plant (SUZUKI Hiroyuki)
 - Chapter 3: milk (EBIHARA Shiho)
 - Chapter 4: wind (SAITÔ Yoshio)
 - Chapter 5: iron (TAGUCHI Yoshihisa)
 - Chapter 6: numeric quantification (KURABE Keita)
 - Chapter 7: tone and accent (IWATA Ray)
 - Chapter 8: it rains (SHIRAI Satoko)

Each chapter also contains 15 articles written by leading researchers on each language or language group, as shown in (2) where the number following the name shows the chapter.

- (2) i. Nivkh (SHIRAIISHI Hidetoshi)
- ii. Ainu (FUKAZAWA Mika)
- iii. Japanese (KISHIE Shinsuke)
- iv. Korean (FUKUI Rei)
- v. Sinitic (UEYA Takashi [6], YAGI Kenji [7], SUZUKI Fumiki 4, 5, [8])
- vi. Hmong-Mien (TAGUCHI Yoshihisa)
- vii. Kra-Dai (ENDO Mitsuaki)
- viii. Tibeto-Burman (SHIRAI Satoko, KURABE Keita, IWASA Kazue, SUZUKI Hiroyuki, EBIHARA Shiho)
- ix. Austroasiatic (KONDO Mika 1, 4, 8, SHIMIZU Masaaki 2, 5, 7, MINEGISHI Makoto 3, 6)
- x. Austronesian (UTSUMI Atsuko)
- xi. Tungusic (MATSUMOTO Ryo) [with Uralic in Ch. 8]
- xii. Uralic (MATSUMOTO Ryo) [with Tungusic in Ch. 8]
- xiii. Mongolic and Turkic (SAITÔ Yoshio)
- xiv. South Asia (YOSHIOKA Noboru)
- xv. Arabic (NAGATO Youichi) [Semitic instead of Arabic in Ch. 4 and 5]

These articles contain a large number of linguistic maps in black and white.¹ The eight color maps in the LAA box correspond to Chapters 1 to 8 in (1). LAA has fifty pages of bibliography, classified by language (group), which give detailed information on the literature cited in the chapters and the primary sources for the maps.

This book is a great contribution to the study of geolinguistics in Asia. Although the range of topics discussed in LAA is not as wide as WALS, the number of data points in Asia described in LAA is far more than that in WALS. For example, Ainu is described as having a simple tone system as a language in WALS (feature 13) while it is reported to have three accent patterns according to dialects in LAA (pitch accent, quantitative accent and none, p. 239).

Below, I will focus on Chapter 7 of LAA, on tone and accent. I will discuss whether the data and descriptions in LAA support the hypothesis in Tokizaki (2019), which

¹ Most of the articles in LAA are based on those in the *Studies in Asian Geolinguistics I to VIII* published electronically by ILCAA (<https://publication.aa-ken.jp>). These original papers include color versions of the maps in LAA.

claims that the stress location in words correlates with the word order of head and complement in the languages of the world.

3. Stress and word order in Asia

3.1. Correlation between word stress and word order

I have been working on the hypothesis that prosody and word order correlate in the languages of the world. This is an extension of holistic typology by Bally (1944) and Donegan and Stampe (1983). Bally compared German and French, and Donegan and Stampe compared Munda and Mon-Khmer in Austroasiatic; they argue that the former has initial stress and head-final order while the latter has final stress and head-initial order. Applying this stress-order correlation to the world's languages in general, Tokizaki (2011) and Tokizaki and Kuwana (2013) argue that languages with word-initial stress tend to have head-final order such as OV while languages with (pen)ultimate stress tend to have head-initial order such as VO.

Tokizaki (2019) investigates Altaic languages (Turkic, Mongolic and Tungusic), which seem to be counterexamples to the hypothesis: most of them have head-final order while a large number of them have been reported to have (pen)ultimate stress (Goedemans and van der Hulst (2005a, b), Schiering and van der Hulst (2010) and Goedemans, Heinz and van der Hulst (2014)). Tokizaki (2019) argues that Altaic languages in fact have word-initial stress and optional word-final pitch accent, the latter of which is sometimes mistaken for word stress/accent. It is argued that Altaic languages have double accent (initial stress and final pitch accent). The idea of word-initial stress is supported by a number of facts: vowel reduction in non-initial syllables, vowel harmony with the initial syllable, alliteration, more variety of vowels in the word-initial position, and emphatic stress/lengthening, emphatic reduplication and gemination of the initial syllable. Thus, Altaic languages are not counterexamples to the generalization that languages with head-final order have word-initial stress.

Tokizaki (2019) focuses on Altaic languages, and does not discuss other languages in Asia in detail. In the next section, I examine the data in Chapter 7 of LAA on tone and accent, and argue that the analysis in Tokizaki (2019) holds true in Asian languages in general.

3.2. Tone and accent in Asia

LAA discusses one phonological aspect of languages, tone and pitch accent, in Chapter 7. The overview is written by IWATA Ray, a leading researcher of Chinese geolinguistics (pp. 232–236). He proposes a division between an inner group and an outer group in order to describe the distribution of suprasegmental features in Asia.

Basically, the inner group is tonal while the outer group is accentual. The map is shown in Fig. 1 (Figure 7.1.1, p. 236).

Fig. 1 Dichotomy of Prosodic Features in Asia (Iwata 2019: 236)

One of the difficulties in the study of accent is the use of the terms. Iwata points out that “the phonetic substance of this term [accent (HT)] varies depending on the authors, probably reflecting the research tradition of each language area” (p. 232).

Prosody including tone and accent shows a wide variation in Asian languages. It is understandable that each paper in this chapter describes the language (group) according to the tradition of the previous studies. If we look at the supplementary map of tone and accent in LAA, we recognize how different the prosody of languages in Asia is.

The eight maps in LAA use different colors to show language groups, e.g. red for Sinitic and dark blue for Uralic. In Map 7, the shape of marks distinguishes prosodic properties such as stress/accent location and the number of phonological tones. However, interpreting what these marks are intended to show is not always straightforward. For example, accent on the penultimate syllable is expressed by a semicircle (upper half) in Austronesian and by an outlined circle in Uralic. The semicircle (upper half) mark used for penult in Austronesian is also used for a variety of simple accent-patterns of Keihan type in Japanese and for 2 to 4 tones in Korean. It would be more user-friendly if all the authors followed the same guideline for using shapes.

Chapter 7 in LAA discusses tone and accent in a wide area of Asia where the languages shown in (2) are spoken. The accompanying map (Map 7) consists of the wide area map, the enlarged map and their legends, which are shown in Figures 2 to 5.

Fig. 2 Tone and Accent in Asia

Fig. 3 Tone and Accent in Asia: enlarged

	Austronesian	Mongolic	Others
△ NT/NA+YC	phonemic length contrast, stress/accnt falling on the last long vowel	Initially-accented	E. Not written
* PA+NP	stress/accnt falling regularly on ultima	Finally-accented	A-1. 2-way Pitch
▢ WT+SA+NP	stress/accnt falling regularly on penult		
▣ WT+YT	stress/accnt falling regularly on antepenult		
● NT/NA+ST+YL	stress/accnt falling on penult, but influence by PAN *e (present day predominantly schewa)	Turkic	Arabic
○ PA+ST+YT	phonomic accent (secondarily introduced)	Finally-accented	A-1. madrasa type
○ ST+SA+NP	phonomic tone		A-2. madrasa type
○ ST+SA+YL		South Asia	A-3. partial lexicalized
▣ WT+RG+YC		tone-accnt - Distinctiveness	B. Maghreb type
(NP: no phonation pattern, NT/NA: no tone or accent, PA: pitch accent, RG: register, SA: stress accent, ST: syllabic tone, WT: word tone, YC: phonation influenced by initial consonants, YL: distinctive phonation, YT: phonetic phonation)		Y	C. tone type
		N	
		Indo-European	
		C. Stress	
		D. Not identified	
		E. Not written	
		A-1. 2-way Pitch	
		B-1. 3-way Tone	
		A-2. 3-way Pitch	
		B-2. 5-way Tone	
		Dravidian	
		D. Not identified	
		E. Not written	
		A-1. 2-way Pitch	
		C. Stress	

	Austronesian	Mongolic	Others
△ NT/NA+YC	phonemic length contrast, stress/accnt falling on the last long vowel	Initially-accented	E. Not written
* PA+NP	stress/accnt falling regularly on ultima	Finally-accented	A-1. 2-way Pitch
▢ WT+SA+NP	stress/accnt falling regularly on penult		
▣ WT+YT	stress/accnt falling regularly on antepenult		
● NT/NA+ST+YL	stress/accnt falling on penult, but influence by PAN *e (present day predominantly schewa)	Turkic	Arabic
○ PA+ST+YT	phonomic accent (secondarily introduced)	Finally-accented	A-1. madrasa type
○ ST+SA+NP	phonomic tone		A-2. madrasa type
○ ST+SA+YL		South Asia	A-3. partial lexicalized
▣ WT+RG+YC		tone-accnt - Distinctiveness	B. Maghreb type
(NP: no phonation pattern, NT/NA: no tone or accent, PA: pitch accent, RG: register, SA: stress accent, ST: syllabic tone, WT: word tone, YC: phonation influenced by initial consonants, YL: distinctive phonation, YT: phonetic phonation)		Y	C. tone type
		N	
		Indo-European	
		C. Stress	
		D. Not identified	
		E. Not written	
		A-1. 2-way Pitch	
		B-1. 3-way Tone	
		A-2. 3-way Pitch	
		B-2. 5-way Tone	
		Dravidian	
		D. Not identified	
		E. Not written	
		A-1. 2-way Pitch	
		C. Stress	

Type	Description	Phonetic Feature	Language Group
Type 2-d.	Tone *A, *C, and *D split	▣	Austronesian
Type 2-e.	All the proto-tones split through devoicing	▣	Austronesian
Type 3.	Tone-split 1 and Tone-split 2 are observed	▣	Austronesian
Kra-Dai		▣	Austronesian
A. Proto type		▣	Austronesian
B. Split caused by consonants		▣	Austronesian
C. Split of tone D		▣	Austronesian
D. Split conditioned by aspirated initial consonants		▣	Austronesian
E. Merger between A ^v and B ^v , A ^l and B ^l		▣	Austronesian
F. C ^l and C ^v are identical		▣	Austronesian
G. B shows no distinction and C ^v =C ^l		▣	Austronesian
H. Bangkok dialect		▣	Austronesian
I. Sakon Nakhon and Wanomiwat dialects		▣	Austronesian
J. others		▣	Austronesian
Tibeto-Burman		▣	Austronesian
WT+NP		▣	Austronesian
ST+NP		▣	Austronesian
ST+YL		▣	Austronesian
NT/NA+NP		▣	Austronesian
RG+YC		▣	Austronesian
ST+YT		▣	Austronesian

Austroasiatic	Tungusic	Uralic
A. Voiced/voiceless contrast in initial consonants	B-1. accent on the last syllable	A-1. accent on the first syllable (fixed)
B. Long/short contrast in vowels	B-2. accent on the last syllable/long vowel	A-2. accent on the first syllable (with exceptions)
C. Initial contrast and registers		B-1. accent on the last syllable
D. Vowel contrast and registers		B-3. accent on the penultimate syllable
E. 2-way contrast in register		C. accent on any syllable
F. 4-way contrast in register		
G. Restructuring of vowels		
H. 2-way contrast in tone		
I. 3-way contrast in tone		
J. 4-way contrast in tone		
K. 5-way contrast in tone		
L. 6-way contrast in tone		

Fig. 5 Tone and Accent in Asia, legend 2

As can be seen in Figs. 2 to 5, the prosody of Asian languages is described in detail. A problem for a typology of prosody is that the prosodic patterns and their descriptions are quite different from language to language. For example, Ainu is described as having pitch accent, quantitative accent or none, while the description of Sinitic is about the number of phonological tones (1 to 6).

In this paper, I focus on the location of word-stress/accent. However, the maps and legends in Figs. 2 to 5 show information on word-stress/accent only in some language groups such as Austronesian, Tungusic, Uralic, Mongolic, Turkic and Arabic. I will refer to other studies than LAA for more data and descriptions of the languages in LAA that lack descriptions about stress.

4. Stress and word order in Asian languages

In this section, I investigate the correlation between word-stress location and word order in each language (groups) shown in (2).

4.1. Nivkh

Nivkh is described as having initial stress and head-final order in WALS. In LAA, Shiraishi (pp. 237-238) shows the durational ratio of the word-initial vowel (stressed) and the second vowel (unstressed) in Amur and Sakhalin dialects (54% to 90 %) on the map. Thus, Nivkh data support the hypothesis that languages with initial stress have head-final order (Tokizaki 2011, 2019).

4.2. Ainu

Ainu has head-final word order. WALS and its source StressTyp2 (Goedemans et al. 2014) make no mention about stress in Ainu. Fukazawa in LAA (pp. 239-240) reports that the majority of Hokkaido dialects have pitch accent on the first or the second syllable while Sakhalin dialects have quantitative accent on a long vowel. She points out that “a long vowel on the open first syllable in Sakhalin often corresponds to a high pitch on the open first syllable in Hokkaido” (e.g. *mīina* (Sakhalin) vs. *mīna* (Hokkaido)). Assuming that vowel length is generally related to stress, I claim that Ainu dialects have word-initial stress/accent rather than word-final stress/accent. Then, Ainu also supports the hypothesis that languages with initial stress have head-final order.

4.3. Japanese

Japanese is a typical head-final language. Its prosody is problematic for the idea that head-final languages have word-initial stress: it has been argued that (Tokyo) Japanese

has no stress but pitch accent on the antepenult mora. In Tokizaki (2022), I argue that a content word in Japanese has the stress on its first mora and an optional pitch-fall accent near its end. If this analysis is on the right track, Japanese also confirms the hypothesis that head-final languages have word-initial stress.

4.4. Korean

Korean is also problematic for the hypothesis that head-final languages have word-initial stress. The nature of stress or accent in Korean has been controversial. Lee, H.-B. (1989), Lee, H.-Y. (1990) and Song (2005) argue that Korean words have stress on the first or the second syllable depending on syllable weight, while de Jong (1994), Jun (1995, 2005) and Lim (2001) argue that Korean stress is not a word-level but a phrase-level stress assigned to the initial syllable in a prosodic phrase. Fukui in LAA (pp. 246–247) does not mention stress in Korean. In Tokizaki (2018), I argue that Korean has both word-level stress and phrase-level stress. I argue that word-level stress is projected to phrase-level stress, which is also in the initial position in the phrase. If this analysis is on the right track, Korean also confirms the hypothesis that head-final languages have word-initial stress.

4.5. Sinitic

Sinitic languages and dialects show interesting geographical distribution. Yagi in LAA (pp. 249–253) discusses the number of tones in Sinitic dialects but not stress and accent. Iwata (2017: 67) draws a map of the tone sandhi types in Chinese dialects, which indicates the location of accent (initial/final), as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 The tone sandhi types in China (Map 1 in Iwata 2017: 67)

This map shows that the tone sandhi in China can be grouped into initial-accented tone sandhi (marked with a square) in the north-west and final-accented tone sandhi (marked with a circle) in the south-east. If we assume that the accented position is the location of stress, we predict that north-west dialects with initial-accent have head-final word order while south-east dialects with final-accent have head-initial order. This prediction is partially borne out by the data from Hashimoto (1978), which show that the northern dialects have some head-final orders (e.g. modifier-head) while the southern dialects have head-initial orders (head-modifier).

4.6. Hmong-Mien

Hmong-Mien languages have head-initial order (e.g. VO & preposition in Hmong Njua) and head-final order (e.g. genitive-noun) according to Dryer (2013a, b, c, d, e, f, g). In WALS, Maddieson (2013) reports that Mien and Hmong Njua have a complex tone system, while there is no information about stress in Goedemans and van der Hulst (2013a, b). Taguchi in LAA (pp. 254–255) discusses tonal types only. Ratliff (2017) points out that the sesquisyllables in Hmong-Mien, as an areal feature relating to Mon-Khmer and Tibeto-Burman, appear in the word-initial syllable. A sesquisyllable makes an iambic foot with the second, full syllable. Then, the head-initial order in Hmong-Mien also supports the idea that head-initial order matches word-final stress. Of course we need to explain why some Hmong-Mien languages also have head-final order in the genitive-noun and numeral-noun constructions. It is interesting that some Hmong-Mien languages also have head-initial order in NP (noun-adjective and noun-demonstrative) while Sinitic dialects typically have head-final NPs (adjective-noun and demonstrative-noun). It seems that mixed word order in NPs in Hmong-Mien shows a gradation from head-final order in the north to head-initial order in the south.

4.7. Kra-Dai

The prosody of Kra-Dai languages is described by Endo in LAA (pp. 256–259). He discusses the distribution of tonal patterns, but not stress in the languages. Peyasantiwong (1986) argues that Tai has stress on the word-final syllable. If we assume that Kra-Dai languages in general have word-final stress, we can explain the fact that the word orders in Kra-Dai are head-initial in most noun phrases as well as in verb phrases. It is also interesting to note that northern dialects (Dong (Southern), Zhuang (Northern), Gelao, Yay, Nung (in Vietnam) and Hlai (Baoding)) have numeral-noun order while southern dialects (Lao and Thai) have noun-numeral order.

4.8. Tibeto-Burman

Tibeto-Burman prosody is described in LAA by Shirai et al. (pp. 260–266). Their description shows a wide variety of tone, accent and phonation in the languages, but

does not show much about stress location. Caplow (2016a) argues that Balti has stress on the second syllable of nouns and stress on the first syllable of verbs. Caplow (2016b) also argues, based on the data of Balti and Rebkong Amdo, that Proto-Tibetan had the same stress pattern. According to the data in Dryer (2013a, b, c, d, e, f, g) most Tibeto-Burman languages have head-final order (OV, postpositional phrase and genitive-noun, suffixing) while many of them also have head-initial order (noun-adjective, noun-demonstrative and noun-numeral).² It might be the case that head-final orders in verb phrases and postpositional phrases relate to the stress on the first syllable in verbs while head-initial orders in noun phrases relate to the stress on the second syllable in nouns. Of course, this is a speculation, which needs to be proved with more research.

It is also promising to investigate the position of neutral tone (or light tone) or sesquisyllable (minor syllable) in a word. Satoko Shirai (personal communication) points out the fact that central Tibetic languages tend to have neutral tone in the word-final position as Mandarin Chinese does, while Burmese has developed sesquisyllables in the word-initial position due to language contact with the Mon language (cf. Matisoff 1973).

4.9. Austroasiatic

Austroasiatic prosody is described by Shimizu in LAA (pp. 267–268), which discusses voiced/voiceless contrast in initial consonants, long/short contrast in vowels, register contrasts, restructuring of vowels and tonal contrasts, but not stress. He does not discuss Munda in this chapter on tone and accent. Donegan and Stampe (1983) is one of the pioneering works investigating the correlation between linguistic rhythm and word order (cf. Bally 1944 for German and French). They compare Munda and Mon-Khmer and argue that Munda has head-final order and initial stress while Mon-Khmer has head-initial order and final stress (cf. Anderson 2015a, b for the idea that Munda has word-final stress and phrase-initial stress). As Dryer (2013a, b, c, d, e, f, g) shows, Munda languages have OV, postposition and noun-final order in NPs (genitive-noun, adjective-noun, demonstrative-noun and numeral-noun) while other genera in Austroasiatic have VO, preposition and noun-initial order in most NPs (noun-genitive, noun-adjective, noun-demonstrative³) except for numeral-noun.⁴ Then, Austroasiatic shows a clear contrast between head-final order & initial-stress and head-initial order & final-stress.

² Karenic languages in the south of the region have preposition rather than postposition.

³ Nicobarese and Khasian have demonstrative-noun order. Mlabri (Minor) has genitive-noun order, and Nicobarese (Car) has adjective-noun order.

⁴ The order of numeral and noun might be problematic because numerals must occur with classifiers in many languages (Dryer 2013g). We need to investigate the structure of noun phrases with classifiers in more detail. Chapter 6 in LAA on numeric quantification gives us much information about the word-order typology.

4.10. Austronesian

The stress/accent of Austronesian is described in detail by Utsumi in LAA (pp. 269–271). She discusses stress/accent in Proto-Austronesian, Formosan and Malayo-Polynesian, Philippine and Indonesian, and concludes that “original Proto-Austronesian stress pattern is retained resulting in the placement of either on the final or the penult syllable” (p. 270). According to Goedemans and van der Hulst (2013a, b) in WALS, Austronesian languages have the following stress locations (the numbers show the number of languages): initial 4, second 1, antepenult 4, penult 62, ultimate 7; left-edge 1, right-oriented 3, right-edge 29. This shows that most Austronesian languages have final stress rather than initial stress.

The word order in most Austronesian languages is head-initial: VO, preposition, noun-genitive 112 (GN 40), noun-adjective and noun-demonstrative. Thus, Austronesian languages support the hypothesis that final-stress languages have head-initial order.

4.11. Tungusic

Matsumoto in LAA (pp. 272–273) reports that “[t]he accent types of all Tungusic languages are classified as type B, in which accent is basically on the last syllable of the word.” One might think that this final-accent is a kind of final-stress. However, he also mentions that “[i]t is often mentioned that the first syllable is pronounced with a relatively strong aspiration and that the last syllable is accompanied with a musical intonation (pitch accent).” These observations match the idea of double accent (initial stress plus final pitch accent) in Altaic proposed by Tokizaki (2019). If we admit word-initial stress in Tungusic (and Altaic in general), we predict that the languages have head-final word order. This prediction is borne out: word order in Tungusic (and Altaic) is consistently head-final: OV, postposition, strongly suffixing, genitive-noun, adjective-noun, demonstrative-noun and numeral-noun. Matsumoto claims that “[g]rammatical features such as vowel harmony, word-formation and inflection based on suffixing, should be considered together for classifying the accent type and the historical changes.” This claim seems to be based on the same idea as Tokizaki (2019), which argues that Altaic initial-stress correlates with vowel harmony and head-final orders including suffixing.

4.12. Uralic

Matsumoto in LAA (p. 274) observes that accent basically falls on the first syllable in Uralic. He classifies Uralic accent patterns into five types according to the location of accent: the first syllable (west area), the first or the second (if the first syllable contains *i/u*) syllable (Mordvin (Moksha), unbounded in WALS), the last syllable

(Udmurt, n.d. in WALS), penultimate (Hill Mari, combined in WALS) and any syllable (Meadow Mari, unbounded in WALS). Matsumoto also points out the language contact between Uralic and Turkic/Tungusic, which changed the prosody of Uralic languages.

The word order of Uralic is head-final (OV, postposition, strongly suffixing, GN, AN, DN and NumN) except for VO in Finnish, Estonian, Hungarian, Saami (Northern), Mordvin (Erzya) and Komi-Zyrian (Dryer 2013a, b, c, d, e, f, g).⁵ Thus, if we assume that Uralic languages have (or originally had) initial stress, they support the hypothesis that languages with initial-stress have head-final order.

4.13. Mongolic and Turkic

Saitô in LAA (pp. 275–276) reports that “which syllable is phonetically prominent in Mongolic languages has been a matter of controversy.” Using vowel reduction and deletion as a criterion for an accent, he claims that the majority of the languages (Mongol, Oirad, and so on) have an accent on the initial syllable while some languages (Monguor, Dongxiang, Kangjia, Bao’an and Shira Yughur in the Gansu and Qinghai provinces) have an accent on the final syllable.

As for Turkic accent, Saitô argues that higher pitch is normally associated with the last syllable in native words. He also points out that “[s]tress, although not well predictable, often falls on the first syllable, but can be placed on other syllables.” This is what I call “double accent” in Tokizaki (2019): Altaic languages have stress in the word-initial position and pitch accent in the word-final position.

Then, we can generalize that Mongolic and Turkic as well as Tungusic typically have word-initial stress. Altaic languages (Mongolic and Turkic and Tungusic) share the property of initial stress and head-final order (OV, postposition, strongly suffixing and modifier-N), supporting the stress-order correlation hypothesis.

4.14. South Asia

Yoshioka in LAA (pp. 277–279) describes tone/accent in the languages in South Asia, which seems to correspond to Indic and Dravidian languages in WALS. He classifies the languages into seven types: 2-way pitch (H/not H), 3-way pitch (H/M/L), 3-way tone (Rise/Fall/Even), 5-way tone, stress, not identified well, and accent not written. However, he does not mention the stress location of stress languages in South Asia. Goedemans and van der Hulst (2013a, b) in WALS give us some information about stress location in Indic: initial (Bengali), ultimate (Kalami, Romani (North Russian)), left-edge (Nepali), right-oriented (Bhojpuri, Maithili, Hindi), right-edge (Awadhi, Gujarati), combined (Sindhi). They also describe the stress location of two Dravidian

⁵ Most VO languages in Uralic are located in the west.

language: initial (Koya), left-edge (Malayalam). We cannot draw any firm conclusions about the stress location in these languages.

The data in Dryer (2013a, b, c, d, e, f, g) show that Indic languages are head-final (OV, postposition, strongly suffixing and modifier-N). We need more data about the stress location to confirm the stress-order correlation hypothesis.

4.15. Arabic

Nagato in LAA (pp. 280–281) observes that “[i]n Arabic, in general, stress falls on the penultimate syllable.” He also points out Maghreb type (with stress shift to the ultimate) and tone type (in Kenya and Uganda).

Word order in Arabic is mostly head-initial: VO, preposition, noun-genitive, noun-adjective (but demonstrative-noun and numeral-noun). Then, Arabic also supports the stress-order correlation hypothesis: languages with final (including penultimate) stress have head-initial order.

4.16. Summary

In this section, I have investigated the languages in Asia in order to confirm the stress-order correlation hypothesis. The summary of the discussion is shown in (3).

(3)	<u>languages</u>	<u>stress</u>	<u>word order</u>
i.	Nivkh	initial	head-final
ii.	Ainu	initial	head-final
iii.	Japanese	initial (+final pitch accent)	head-final
iv.	Korean	initial or second	head-final
v.	Sinitic (north-west)	initial	head-final
	Sinitic (south-east)	final	head-initial
vi.	Hmong-Mien	final	head-initial (final in NP)
vii.	Kra-Dai	final?	head-initial (final in Num)
viii.	Tibeto-Burman	initial in V, second in N	head-final (initial in NP)
ix.	Austroasiatic	final	head-initial
	AA (Munda)	initial	head-final
x.	Austronesian	final	head-initial
xi.	Tungusic	initial	head-final
xii.	Uralic	initial	head-final
xiii.	Mongolic & Turkic	initial	head-final
xiv.	South Asia (Indic)	initial/final	head-final
	SA (Dravidian)	initial	head-final
xv.	Arabic	penultimate	head-initial

The result of this survey show the stress-order correlation generally holds in Asian languages: languages with initial stress have head-final order while languages with final stress have head-initial order. Of course we need to investigate the nature of prosody in some language groups (3iii, iv, vii, viii, xiv).

5. Why does stress location correlate with word order?

Finally, let us consider why stress location correlates with word order. Tokizaki (2011 et seq.) argues that a language “chooses” either head-initial or head-final order according to its stress pattern. In the minimalist program of generative grammar, Chomsky (1995, 2012 et seq.) assumes that linear order of constituents is determined at the interface between syntax and phonology. For example, syntax makes a structure (a set) without linear order by merging a head X and its complement YP (a phrase headed by Y, e.g. object, modifier) as in (4).

$$(4) \quad \{X \ YP\}$$

This structure is linearized either head-initial (5a) or (5b).

$$(5) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{a.} & [X \ \mathbf{Y}P] \\ \text{b.} & [\mathbf{Y}P \ X] \end{array}$$

In (5), the complement YP receives the main stress in the constituent because YP consists of a head Y and its complement: Cinque (1993) claims that stress falls on the most deeply embedded element in a structure, which is in YP. I assume that the word stress pattern is projected onto the phrasal stress pattern in a language: languages with word-initial stress have phrase-initial stress while languages with word-final stress have phrase-final stress. Then, the phrase-final stress in (5a) is chosen by languages with word-final stress (6a) while the phrase-initial stress in (5b) is chosen by languages with word-initial stress (6b).

$$(6) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{a.} & [\text{Word } \sigma \ (\cdot) \ \sigma] \\ \text{b.} & [\text{Word } \sigma \ (\cdot) \ \sigma] \end{array}$$

Thus, languages with word-final stress (6a) have head-initial order with phrase-final stress (5a) while languages with word-initial stress (6b) have head-final order with

phrase-initial stress (5b). I argue that this is why word-stress correlates with word order in languages of the world. For the detail of this idea, see Tokizaki (2011 et seq.) and Tokizaki and Okazaki (2022).

6. Conclusion

In this paper, I have investigated the correlation between word-stress location and word order in Asian languages referring to the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia* (LAA). In section 2, I briefly reviewed WALS and LAA. In section 3, I illustrated Chapter 7 on tone and accent in Asia in LAA. In Section 4, I discussed the stress location and word order in each language group in Asia based on the descriptions in LAA and other data in literature including WALS. In Section 5, I explained the reason why word-stress location is correlated with word order.

This paper is an attempt to prove the hypothesis that languages with initial stress have head-final order (e.g. OV) while languages with final stress have head-initial order (e.g. VO). We have seen that the hypothesis is supported by most language groups in Asia. Of course we need to examine the prosodic system of each language (group), which has not been investigated well. I hope that this study will make a contribution to the study of geolinguistics and linguistic theory.

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